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Research Article

ASSESSMENT OF DEPRESSION AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS OF SHEIKH ZAYED HOSPITAL RAHIM YAR KHAN

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Abstract:

Introduction: Depression is psychological disorder that affects the person's mood, physical functions and social interactions. Medical students remain under stress that often exerts a negative effect on the academic performances, physical health and psychological well-being of students. Pakistan is developing country and depression among students of this country has a bad effect on its struggle to excellence.

Objectives: i) To determine rate of depression among medicals students of SZMC. ii) To observe and association between depression and academic year. iii) To observe an association between and academic output. iv) To observe and association between depression and physical problems.

Study Design: Cross-sectional descriptive study.

Setting: The study was carried out in Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan.

Duration of Study: It was from April to 30 May 2015.

Subjects and Methods: 100 students, both males and females of Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan were included in the studies. A redesigned questionnaire and counting sampling technique were used to collect the data.

Results: Total depressed students were 44%. There was high prevalence of depression in females 60% while in males was 46%. There were 41% students who were non depressed, 22% students were mildly depressed. 14% were moderately depressed and 22% severely depressed. Analysis of depression with age revealed that the prevalence of depression was equal among 18 to 21 years of age group and 26 to 28 years of age group which is highest 100%.

Conclusion: High level of depression was found in our students during the initial 2 years of their course. It poses additional challenges for student's support service delivery. The present study concludes the depression rate is 59% among medical students.

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INTRODUCTION:

Depression is a common mental disorder that presents with depressed mood, loss of interest or pleasure, feeling of guilt or low-self-worth, disturbed sleep or appetite, low energy, and poor concentration.

Depression causes a very high rate of diseases. Burden is expected to show a rising trend during the coming 20 years. It is a significant public health problem with relatively common, high prevalence and its recent nature profoundly disrupts patient lives. General population surveys conducted in many parts of the world in which 15 to 20% children and adolescents suffered from it that are almost similar to that of adult populations.

Medical education is perceived as being stressful. It has been observed that medical students experience a high incidence of personal distress during their undergraduate course. High level of stress may have a negative effect on mastery of the academic curriculum. Stress, health and emotional problems increase during the period of undergraduate medical education.

This can lead to mental distress and has a negative impact on cognitive functioning and learning. The intense pressures and relentless demand of medical education may impair students behavior, diminish learning, destroy personal relationships. Studies suggest that throughout training. It is not just undergraduate study period which brings the stress but it may continue later in internship, postgraduate study period and later in physicians, practical life and it may reach burnout level. Medical education is being perceived as being stressful. Stress during education leads to mental distress and have a negative impact on cognitive functioning and learning.

Medical college stress is likely to predict later mental health problems but students seldom seek help for their problems. It is important for student of stress which not only affects his health but also his academic achievement at different time points of their study period. The objective of this study was to determine the prevalence of depression among medical students of SZMC and to identify its associated factors.

Characteristics of a mentally healthy person: Mental Health is not mere absence of mental illness. A healthy person has three main characteristics.

1. He feels comfortable about himself, that is, he feels reasonably secure and adequate. He neither

underestimates nor overestimates his own ability. He accepts his shortcomings. He has self-respect.

2. The mentally healthy person feels right towards others. This means that he is able to be interested in other and to love them. He has friendships that are satisfying and lasting. He is able to feel a part of a group without being submerged by it. He is able to like and trust others. He takes responsibility for his neighbors and his fellow – men.
3. The mentally healthy person is able to meet the demands of life. He does something about the problems as they arise. He is able to think for himself and to take his own decisions. He sets reasonable goals for himself. He shoulders his daily responsibilities. He is not bowled over by his own emotions of fear, anger, love or guilt.

OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the rate of depression among medical students of Sheikh Zayed Medical College, Rahim Yar Khan.
2. Observe and association between depression and academic year.
3. Observe an association between depression and academic output.
4. Observe and association between depression and physical problems.

METHODOLOGY:

Setting: Sheikh Zayed Medical College, Rahim Yar Khan.

Duration of Study: It was from 27th April to 30th May 2015.

Study Population: Medical students of Sheikh Zayed Medical College, Rahim Yar Khan

Study Design: This study was a cross sectional study that was used to measure the prevalence of depression, stress and related factors among the Medical students for all years.

Sample Size: Study was conducted on 100 Medical students half of them were females and other half were male. The study technique used was stratified sampling, in which 20 students from each class were selected randomly.

Inclusion Criteria: All the medical students of Sheikh Zayed Medical College, Rahim Yar Khan, who were willing to give data.

Data Criteria: Unwilling students were excluded.

Data Collection: Study was conducted on 100 students, Redesigned questionnaire containing variables like name, age, gender, residence, health status, sleep habits, studies, daily activities, temperament and academic year was used to collect

the data regarding prevalence of depression among medical students.

Data Analysis: Data was entered into computerized SPSS software and various results were obtained.

Table No.01: Age Statistics (years)

Mean	21.22
Std. Error of Mean	.210
Median	21.00
Mode	21
Std. Deviation	2.097
Minimum	18
Maximum	28

Table No.01 shows that mean age of depression is 21.22 years with a range of 18-28 years.

Table No.02: Age Statistics (years)

Age	Frequency	Percent (%)
18-20	40	40.0
21-23	46	46.0
24-26	13	13.0
27+	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Table No.2 shows that the prevalence of depression was highest among 21-23 age group followed by 18-20 age group.

Table No.03: Score for Depression According to residence

Residence	Score for depression				Total
	Non-Depressed	Midly depressed	Moderately depressed	Severely depressed	
Day Scholars	13	2	0	1	15
Hostel ides	35	23	13	14	85
Total	47	25	13	15	100

Table No.3 shows that the host elides suffer from depression more than the day scholars.

Table No.04: Score for Depression According to Health

Good health	Score for depression				Total
	Non-Depressed	Mildly depressed	Moderately depressed	Severely depressed	
Better than usual	16	7	1	0	24
Same as usual	4	7	8	8	27
Worse than usual	0	1	1	5	7
Much worse than usual	27	10	3	2	42
Total	47	25	13	15	100

Table No.4 shows that almost 42% of the students stated that their health was much worse than usual.

Table No.05: Score for Depression According to Temperament

Edgy and Bd tempered	Score for depression				Total
	Non-Depressed	Mildly depressed	Moderately depressed	Severely depressed	
Not at all	15	6	3	2	26
No more than usual	5	12	7	5	29
Rather more than usual	2	2	2	8	14
Much more than usual	25	5	1	0	31
Total	47	25	13	15	100

Table No.05 shows that 31% students conveyed that they feel edgy and bad tempered much more than usual.

Table No.06: Score for Depression According to Daily Activities

Daily Activities	Score for depression				Total
	Non-Depressed	Mildly depressed	Moderately depressed	Severely depressed	
More than usual	2	11	6	6	25
Same us usual	0	0	2	6	8
Less than usual	18	6	0	0	24
Much less than usual	27	8	5	3	43
Total	47	25	13	15	11

Table No.06 shows that 43% students have daily activities much less than usual.

Table No.07: Score for Depression According to Studies

Difficulty to concentrate on studies	Score for depression				Total
	Non-Depressed	Mildly depressed	Moderately depressed	Severely depressed	
Not at all	24	9	5	1	39
No more than usual	7	9	3	1	20
More than usual	7	5	4	13	29
Much more than usual	9	2	1	0	12
Total	47	25	13	15	100

Table No.07 shows that 12% of the students have difficulty to concentrate on their studies much more than usual.

Table No.08: Suicidal thoughts due to depression

Suicidal thoughts	Score for depression				Total
	Non-Depressed	Mildly depressed	Moderately depressed	Severely depressed	
Not at all	47	21	11	5	87
On and off	0	4	2	10	16
Total	47	25	13	15	100

Table No.08 shows that 16% of the students have suicidal thoughts due to depression.

Table No.09: Score for Depression According to Change in Appetite

Change in appetite	Score for depression				Total
	Non-Depressed	Mildly depressed	Moderately depressed	Severely depressed	
Not at all	6	10	8	7	31
No more than usual	1	0	1	4	6
Less than usual	25	6	0	2	33
Much less than usual	15	9	4	2	30
Total	47	25	13	15	100

Table No.09 shows that 30% of the students have decreased appetitive due to depression.

Table No.10: Score for Depression According to Change in Sleeping Habits.

Change in sleeping habits	Score for depression				Total
	Non-Depressed	Mildly depressed	Moderately depressed	Severely depressed	
Not at all	11	8	1	8	28
Less than usual	23	12	9	4	48
More than usual	11	2	0	1	14
Much more than usual	2	3	3	2	10
Total	47	25	12	15	100

Table No.10 shows that 10% of the students have change in their sleeping habits.

Table No.11: Score for Depression According to Sex

Score for depression	Sex		Total
	Female	Male	
Non-depressed	22	25	47
Mildly depressed	10	15	25
Moderately depressed	12	1	13
Severely depressed	6	9	15
Total	50	50	100

Table No.11 shows that depression was significantly associated with the female gender.

DISCUSSION:

According to age statistics, mean age of depression is 21.22 with a range of 18-28 (Table No.1) Analysis of depression with age showed that the prevalence of depression was highest amount 21-23 age grouped (46%) followed by 18-20 age group (40%) (Table No.2) Study results showed that hostelides suffered from depression more than the day scholars (Tables No.3) Almost 42% of the depressed students stated that their health was much worse than usual (Table No.4) and 31% conveyed that they feel edgy and bad tempered much more than usual due to depression (Table No.5) 43% of the depressed students have day to day activities much less than usual (Table No.6) only 12% of the depressed students have difficulty to concentrate on their studies much more than usual (Table No.7) According to the survey 16% of the students have suicidal thoughts due to depression (Table No.8) 30% of the student have decreased appetitie due to depression (Table No.9) 10% of depressed students have change in sleeping habits more than usual (Table No.10) Depression was significantly associated with the female gender i.e 56% (Table No.11) Overall prevalence of severely depressed students was 15% in all the five classes (Table No.12) and there were 47% students who were non depressed, 25% students were mildly depressed, 13% were moderately depressed and 15% severely depressed. The prevalence of depression among Sheikh Zayed Medical students was 53% (Table No.13)

A descriptive self-administered questionnaire-based study got a response rate of 100% which provided an adequate sample size to fulfill the objective of this study. The result of this study indicated higher prevalence of stress in our undergraduate students. The level of stress or de pression varied between stages of education. This Increased level of stress indicated a decrease of psychological health in our students which any impairs student's behavior, diminishes learning, and ultimately affect patient care.

CONCLUSION:

This study presents empirical evidence regarding the psychological health of students in our college. These findings suggest that high level of depression exist in our students during the initial 3 years of their course and pose additional challenges for students support services delivery. This suggests that when students are taken into colleges, special care has to be taken to find out obvious psychiatric problems or just psychological distress in them. The major finding is that psychological distress in students is more common than population-based estimate; therefore, it may require to address mental health problems along with common health strategies for our students. It is important to detect depression at an early stage so that treatment could be given to affected persons.

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